

THE INFLUENCE OF AA5083 SURFACE TREATMENTS ON THE INTERFACE BONDING PERFORMANCE BETWEEN AA5083 AND EPOXY

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ABSTRACT

This paper adopts anodic oxidation, sandblasting and silane coupling agent (KH560) to deal with the AA5083 surface, studying the influence of surface treatments on the bonding performance of AA5083 aluminum with cryogenic adhesives and comparing with the samples that are only dealt with isopropyl alcohol cleaning. Using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to observe and analyze the surface of parent metal and fracture section of bonding samples, Test the shear strength of joints, roughness and contact angles whose surfaces are dealt with sandblasting, anodic oxidation and silane coupling agent. FTIR is used to detect the chemical reaction in which Si-O-Al chemical bond is born to improve the interfacial bond strength.

1 INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of modern society leads to increasing demand for natural gas, natural gas transportation and storage problems are increasingly brought to the attention of the people. The key technology of manufacturing LNG carrier is the design and manufacture to solve the liquid cargo system maintenance, and how to realize the thermal insulation material and the storage tank with metal materials is one of the key links. Existing connection technology, compared with riveting and welding, bonding has obvious advantages. Glue joint has simple process, low cost, low stress concentration, thus it is suitable for liquid cargo system maintenance in the metal substrate with thermal insulation. If the state of Metal surface is different, the glue joint performance of the joint also will make a big difference, particularly on the joint strength. And study different methods of surface treatment on the properties of adhesive joint effect has the very high application value. On this basis, study the effect of anodic oxidation, sandblasting and treating with silane coupling agent surface treatment technology of aluminum alloy on AA5083 / low temperature glue glue joint performance, and provide a reliable experimental data for cargo maintenance system to make sure the strength between metal substrate and heat-insulating material.

2 APPROCH

Under the conditions of electrolyte temperature of 40 °C, the voltage on 20 V, oxidation time for 20 min, we use the method of phosphoric acid - sulfuric acid anodic oxidation to treat the AA5083; sandblast on AA5083 aluminum alloy, ensuring sand blasting pressure: 0.4 MPa, sand blasting distance: 60 mm, sandblasting Angle: 15° , sand grain diameter of 150; prepare the concentration of 1% KH560 alcohol diluent, immerse AA5083 aluminum alloy 2 min in the diluent, take out and heat it under 120 °C. We use the samples which have been treated with the above three ways to prepare single lap shear specimens.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 Symbol and corresponding surface treatment

Symbol	Substrate	Surface treatment
Al	Pristine Al	Acetone cleaning
Al+A	Pristine Al	Anodizing
Al+S	Pristine Al	Sand blasting
Al+S+SCA	Al+S	Treated by silane coupling agent (KH560)
Al+A+SCA	Al+A	Treated by silane coupling agent (KH560)

Fig.1 SEM images showing (a) Al, (b) Al+S, (c) Al+A, (d) Al+SCA

Fig. 1 shows the SEM images of the surface of the original AA5083 alloy, sand AA5083

alloy, anodised AA5083 alloy and AA5083 alloy treated by silane coupling agent. There are rolling stripe and crack defects on the surface of the original AA5083 alloy with no surface treatment. Moreover, the aluminum alloy surface is smooth in Fig1 (a). The surface microscopic appearance of the aluminum alloy after sand blasting is shown in Fig.1 (b).Some microcraters appear and make the surface of AA5083 aluminum alloy bumpy. The existence of microcraters not only increases the surface area of aluminum alloy, but also makes the adhesion strength improve when applying cryogenic adhesives to the micropit. Generally aluminum alloy surface will cover a layer of thin film with uniform microporous. The pore diameter and porosity of oxide film is not only related to electrolyte kinds, but also the oxidation voltage, electrolyte temperature and oxidation time. Anodic oxidation of experimental parameters for voltage 20 V, temperature 40°C, the microporous structure of the time when 20 min is shown in Fig1(c). Hole system is conducive to the adhesive molecules and coupling agent molecules into them, and ultimately improve the bonding strength. As shown in Fig.1(d), hydrolysis of silane coupling agent forming network structure covers the surface of aluminium alloy. Silane coupling agent improves the strength of the interface by forming chemical bonds with aluminum alloy and reacting with cryogenic adhesives.

Fig.2 Contact angle of the surface to aluminum alloy with cryogenic adhesives

According to the young's equation: $Y_{SV} - Y_{SL} = Y_{LV} \cos \vartheta$, in order to obtain higher surface energy, the AA5083 surface should have smaller contact angles. The surface of AA5083 alloy without surface treatment is smooth, the contact angle measured in laboratory is 49.13 °; After sandblasting processing, contact angle with cryogenic adhesives is 21.68 °; Contact angle of aluminum alloy with cryogenic adhesives is 22.38 ° while anodic oxidation process parameters is 20V,40°C,20min. Surface wettability of the cryogenic epoxy resin glue to the surface on untreated aluminum alloy is poorer, the contact angles for anodic oxidation samples and sand blasting samples show that it is better for the wettability of cryogenic adhesives to the AA5083 after anodic oxidation treatment.

Fig.3 Contour curve of the surface on AA5083 without surface treatment

Fig.4 Contour curve of the surface on AA5083 after sand blasting

Fig.5 Contour curve of the surface on AA5083 after anodic oxidation

As shown in Fig.3, Fig.4 and Fig.5, there are a few of peaks in the trough and the field of the wave is wide. Meanwhile the waves are undulating and fluctuating. The wave and trough of contour curve for sandblasting and anodized samples are meticulous and in a relatively stable area. While contour curve is more stable, less volatile. The contour curve of the original AA5083 surface is shown in Fig.3. The overall surface of AA5083 is smooth and the roughness value is only 0.139 μm. Fig.4 is the contour curve of AA5083 surface after sand blasting. The abrasive grain has the effect on cutting and cleaning of aluminum alloy, aluminum alloy surface oxidation film and impurity have been cleaned up, the surface has become concave and uneven, and roughness also becomes large. The roughness values is 1.502μm. Fig.5 shows the contour curve of AA5083 surface after anodic oxidation. The surface of the AA5083 aluminum alloy after anodization has been flattened and uneven, and the roughness value is 1.040 μm.

Fig.6 FTIR spectrum showing the situation for interface of Al+SCA

The spectra in Fig.6 proved that the coupling agent reacts with inorganic substance. The chemical interaction is between coupling agent hydrolysate and AA5083 aluminum alloy sheet, and it produced Si-O-Al chemical bond which was near at 900-1000cm⁻¹.

Fig.7 Single lap shear strength of Al, Al+S, Al+S+SCA, Al+A, Al+A+SCA at different low temperature

As shown in Fig.7, sample shearing strength follows the same pattern in which the strength respectively is Al+A+SCA, Al+A, Al+S+SCA, Al+S, Al from the big to the small at -60°C and -120°C. While at 0°C, strength(Al+S+SCA) is smaller than strength (Al+S), strength (Al+A+SCA) is smaller than strength (Al+A). Maybe 0°C is a critical state of silane coupling

agent like water turning into ice, performance of silane coupling agent has changed at 0°C, so the strength of samples after treated by silane coupling agent changes to smaller. When the temperature is 25°C, $\text{strength(Al+S+SCA)} < \text{strength(Al+S)}$, while $\text{strength(Al+A+SCA)} > \text{strength(Al+A)}$ which suggests that coupling agent plays a role on improving the bonding strength of the interface.

4 CONCLUSION

At room temperature, the surface energy of parent metal is low and the shear strength of joints is 7.23MPa; sandblasting removes all kinds of impurities and oxide films of parent metal, the shear strength has been improved 151.45% compared with the samples that are only dealt with isopropyl alcohol cleaning; after anodic oxidation, the surface of AA5083 aluminum alloy formed the pore of Al_2O_3 and the shear strength has been improved 194.74% compared with the samples that are only dealt with isopropyl alcohol cleaning; A kind of chemical bond (Si-O-Al) has formed on the surface of AA5083 after treating with KH560, the shear strength has also been improved compared with the samples that are only dealt with anodic oxidation or sandblasting.

Under low temperature, along with the dropping of temperature, the shear strength of the bonding samples which are dealt with different surface treatments increased first, then decreased, and when the temperature is -120°C, the shear strength of Al+A+SCA reached the 33.96MPa which is the highest.

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